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Teaching the management of innovation to engineers

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ABSTRACT

The literature on the management of innovation has strongly emphasised the need for a complex and wide set of competences to successfully manage technological innovation within companies. This paper provides eight years of experience teaching industrial engineers how to integrate technical and non-technical skills in the management of technological innovation. The paper presents the experience of a design based learning course for industrial engineers concerning the New Product Development (NPD) process. The course has been offered to around 400 master students. As an initial result, the paper proposes a model for designing courses on innovation and new product development, useful for engineering schools. In addition, our study suggests that design based learning (DBL) seems to be effective for developing the ability to integrate technical engineering and non-engineering skills, and for developing professional “soft” skills, as well. The DBL approach seems to be less effective for supporting the specialisation of technical competences.

Conference Key Areas: Engineering Skills, Attractiveness of Engineering Education
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Keywords: Innovation management, Engineering skills, Managerial skills,
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INTRODUCTION

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The literature on the management of innovation has strongly emphasised the need for a complex and wide set of competences for successfully managing technological innovation within companies [1] [2]. In fact, along the innovation funnel, several competences, other than engineering ones, become critical: managerial, organisational, and relational competences are especially relevant. This is also confirmed by the many empirical studies that bring into evidence that the high failure rate of technology-based start-ups is mainly due to a lack of managerial competencies, rather than to a lack of financial resources or technical competences [3].

A way to face the problem is to provide engineers with the necessary skills to effectively communicate with other people. At times, this has been interpreted as the need to introduce “soft” skills, and/or “professional” skills [4; 5; 6]. We argue that some of the complementary skills necessary to engineers to successfully manage technological innovation are not only the “soft” or “professional” ones. Engineers also need the “hard” skills related to economic, financial, organisational and marketing matters. This paper provides eight years of teaching experience aimed at providing industrial engineers with the tools needed to integrate technical and non-technical skills in the management of technological innovation.

Starting from an analysis of the innovation process within companies –called the “innovation funnel”- the set of competences necessary in each phase of the funnel was identified. Then, in coherence with the results of this study, a program was defined for teaching the management of innovation to engineers, not only in terms of topics to be introduced, but also in terms of teaching methodology. Active learning was considered the best way to ensure the actual integration of technical and non-technical competences. It is not simply a matter of juxtaposition of competences, but of integration [7]. Students were asked to generate an idea for re-designing an existing product and to actually design the development, manufacturing and commercialisation phases of the innovation process. They were also asked to present and discuss their work with a committee of external experts who were able to evaluate the industrial feasibility and quality of their projects.

The paper explores the results achieved by around 400 students involved in the program whose work was evaluated by external experts in terms of real ability to integrate technical and non-technical skills.

The paper is structured as follows: section 1 gives the theoretical background; section 2 clarifies the research question and the context of the study; section 3 describes and discusses the study results; section 4 gives some final conclusions.

1. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

The theoretical background of this paper relies on two fields of study. Research on the management of innovation was investigated in order to define the set of competences needed by engineers in order to successfully contribute to innovation processes. Research on active learning is the reference for defining the methodology of the teaching program.

1.1. Innovation as a managerial process

Technology innovation as a managerial process can be dated back to the ‘80s and ‘90s, when innovation started to be considered an endogenous variable for companies. Before that, in neoclassical economics and traditional industrial economics, technological innovation was mainly conceived of as an exogenous variable. As a result, managerial problems were related mainly to internal R&D

efficiency and information gathering. During the '80s, within the evolutionary economics approach [8], and especially in the '90s, within the resource-based [9] and the competence-based approaches [10], technology innovation became a managerial process that needed to be properly managed in order to support a company's long-term success. This literature also brings into evidence the relevance, for both the individual and the organization, of how learning, competences and skills are fundamental determinants of innovation.

In its Oslo Manual [11], the OECD defines innovation as “the implementation of a new or significantly improved product (good or service), or process, a new marketing method, or a new organisational, method in business practices, workplace organisation or external relations.” It describes innovation activities as “all scientific, technological, organisational, financial and commercial steps which actually, or are intended to, lead to the implementation of innovations.” It is thus evident that the management of innovation requires a wide set of competences.

Moving from a general definition, technology innovation within companies can be represented by the innovation funnel [12] shown in figure 1.

Figure 1. The innovation funnel [12]

The innovation funnel includes a phase of investigation of new ideas and technological opportunities, after which the development of an innovative product and/or process and/or service is developed. All along the funnel there is a selection process, according to which ideas and opportunities are gradually screened and selected according to strategic, technical and economic criteria. For many reasons, the innovation funnel takes specific characteristics. So, its slope, total duration and the specific activities conducted in each phase can change significantly.

It is important for companies to be able to properly manage the whole funnel, as the return of all the investments are actually achieved at the end of the funnel, when something new is commercialised. Certainly, technical competences that focus on the specific object of innovation are necessary to successfully manage the innovation process, but they are not sufficient. In order to draw economic benefits from innovation, creativity, problem-solving, economic and managerial skills, marketing know-how and tools are fundamental as well [1].

1.2. Active learning for the management of innovation

Teaching innovation is not only a matter of contents, but also of methods. The literature proposes even the concept of Innovation Pedagogy, a learning approach based upon constructivism that “utilizes academic staff innovation competences and ensures students’ active involvement in innovation processes” [23]. According to innovation pedagogy, active involvement of students is necessary to link academic

skills to practice. Reflections on the methods for teaching innovation also come from the field on entrepreneurship learning [24; 25]. This stream of literature confirms the need for active learning in order to “train individuals to act entrepreneurially” [24]. In particular, teaching innovation and entrepreneurship to engineers poses the problem of providing them with the necessary business and cross-disciplinary skills, especially in a global competitive context [25]. And that requires a balanced learning approach including classes as well as exercises, fieldworks, involvement in actual projects. Active learning refers to all teaching approaches in which students are directly engaged in learning activities [13], including problem- and project-based learning [14]. Active learning is recognised to be particularly relevant for supporting the acquisition of skills such as team working, conflict management, problem-solving, communication, and coordination [15] [16]. Within the several approaches to active learning, Problem-Based Learning (PBL) stimulates the acquisition of inquiry skills and the integration of theoretical knowledge by engaging students in solving ill-defined, open-ended, interdisciplinary problems [14] [17]. Among PBL approaches, in DBL students are involved in a project-planning process, in which they are assigned the task to develop an end product, an object. Such an involvement is thus characterised by the six features described by Wijnen [18]: professionalization, activation, co-operation, creativity, integration, and multi-disciplinarity. DBL is an active learning method in which “students gather and apply knowledge while designing creative and innovative practical solutions” ([17]. All the characteristics described above make DBL especially suitable for teaching the management of innovation to engineers. Indeed, DBL allows for achieving and integrating interdisciplinary competences, of both the technical and non-technical sorts.

2. RESEARCH QUESTION AND CONTEXT OF THE STUDY

2.1. Research question

Starting from the premises drawn from the literature with regards to the multidisciplinary of innovation management and the suitability of design based learning for such a topic, the research question becomes: how can a course on the management of innovation for engineers be designed? Two sub-questions arise: How to identify the appropriate set of competences? and How to design a learning method able to foster the integration of the required technical and non-technical skills?

2.2. Context of the study: the course on Industrial Design

The questions were studied in the context of a course for graduate students in industrial engineering, which was designed and launched in 2007 at University Cattaneo in Italy and monitored over an eight year period. The course is dedicated to a specific type of innovation: NPD [19] and it is labelled “Industrial Design”. It is held within a master program on Industrial Engineering and it is offered to interested graduates in industrial engineering, or any technical engineering field (bio-medical, mechanical, electronic, etc.). NPD is the process that leads to the commercial launch of a new or improved product onto the market. The course is thus aimed at teaching students how to successfully identify an idea for a new (or improved) product and how to manage it until its launch onto the market. It is given at the end of the master program and thus provides students with the opportunity to exploit all the competencies acquired in their previous courses and to integrate them with those specifically concerned with innovation management, having a strong practical focus.

2.3. Course design: competencies

To identify the set of competencies needed by engineers to manage the innovation process, we started from the innovation funnel and the related activities, with specific reference to the NPD process. In coherence with Eppinger and Ulrich [19], the funnel of the NPD process can be conceived as composed of four main phases: concept development, product design, process design, and commercialisation.

The early phases of the NPD process are concerned with idea and concept generation. In this part of the funnel the market and the competitive environment are investigated in order to identify potential unsatisfied needs. The technological environment is also investigated, in order to identify technological innovations and trends potentially useful for market needs. In coherence with the market and technology investigation, a first tentative design of the new product is put forward, which is then tested and experimented by means of models or prototypes. The commercialisation of the new product should also be conceived in terms of target pricing and distribution channels, as these strongly influence the product and process design phases. After the concept design phase, the phase of development includes the engineering and the manufacturing phases, i.e, product design and process design. In the product design phase, the product's architecture, components and subsystems are defined, together with the final assembly scheme. Simultaneously, suppliers are identified and cost analysis is conducted. In the process design phase, the tools and machineries to be used in the production process are defined, together with the procedures for quality assurance and process control. As the NPD process should generate value for the company, a Business Plan of the whole initiative must be provided to decision makers, who must synthesise not only the main features of the products, but also its impact on the company's revenues and costs. This certainly influences the definition of price, and of all the costs of the manufacturing and commercialisation processes. The various phases of the NPD process are not strictly sequential: the concurrent engineering approach suggests, whenever possible, to conduct them partially in parallel, in order to exploit feedback throughout the different stages and anticipate problems.

The set of competencies necessary for the NPD process are synthesised in table 1. As can be seen, the course of Industrial Design was organised in four sets of contents: concept development, product design, process design, business plan.

Table 1. The NPD process phases and the related competences

Phases of the NPD process competencies	Concept development	Product design	Process design	Business plan
Technical engineering competencies	Technical know-how about the specific product; product modelling; prototyping;	Technical know-how about the specific product (materials and functionality); manufacturing technologies, assembly issues;	Technical know-how about the specific product; manufacturing technologies, assembly issues; quality issue; control issues;	Technical know-how about the specific product;

Technical non engineering competencies	Competitive environment strategic analysis; technology intelligence; marketing	Cost analysis; management accounting; supplier evaluation; purchasing	Cost analysis; management accounting; manufacturing organisational issues;	Financial accounting; marketing; management accounting;
Professional and soft skills	Creativity; awareness of the external environment	Awareness of the external environment; coordination	Coordination;	Communication; coordination; awareness of the external environment

2.4. Course design: learning methodology

An active learning approach is adopted in order to favour the actual integration of all the competencies necessary in NPD. In particular, a design based learning approach is adopted, in which students are actually engaged in solving an ill-defined problem by designing something new. In the Industrial Design course, students are asked to generate some ideas for improving an existing product and to develop the new product concept, define the product and process designs and build a business plan of the overall initiative. Just to give a few examples of the products studied, students' projects have concerned the redesign of a vacuum cleaner, an electronic transformer, etc. The work is conducted in groups of 4 or 5 people, which are formed by the students themselves. The course is organised according to the four parts of the NPD process: concept development, product design, process design, business plan. For each part, some sessions are dedicated to theory, after which a set of tutorial sessions are offered, during which each group works on its own project. In total, the course provides 12 ECTS credits in around 100 hours, 50% of which are based on theory, and the other 50% dedicated to tutoring for the projects. Each teacher is specialised in the specific phase of the NPD process, not only in terms of theoretical knowledge, but also in terms of professional practice. Hence, the improved, re-designed product studied by students develops from the idea to the final industrial version, while respecting the business plan, all throughout the period of the course. All the technical and non-technical hard skills are thus used on a real product. Real problems need to be solved and students themselves have to choose the specific theoretical tools to be implemented. Hence, students can appreciate the skills they are using to successfully manage their project. The involvement of students in all the phases of the NPD process allows them to conduct the phases in parallel whenever possible, in coherence with the concurrent engineering approach. Furthermore, working in a group should favour the development of professional and soft skills, in particular those regarding conflict management, coordination and communication.

2.5. Course design: evaluation process

The evaluation process is divided in two parts: an individual written theory test and the group project evaluation. The individual test includes open theoretical questions concerning all the topics and issues presented during the course. The evaluation of group projects is based upon five elements: four written reports, and a final presentation. The four written reports describe how students have conducted the four phases of their project. An evaluation for each report is provided by the pertinent instructor. The final presentation is discussed with a committee of professionals, who are qualified to evaluate the industrial feasibility and quality of the projects. Involving

professionals, who directly participated in innovation processes, is fundamental for ensuring the multidisciplinary skills to successfully participate to the innovation process [23]. Students should convince the committee that the project is actually worthy, feasible, in line with market needs and economically sustainable. Soft and professional skills concerning team working, effective communication, interdisciplinary abilities, and awareness of the external environment [5] are also evaluated during the presentations.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Students' results

In this section a quantitative synthesis of the results is given. Given the exploratory (and theory building) nature of this study, this is given to provide a comprehensive picture of the students' performance, and it is not aimed at validating the proposed teaching approach. Table 2 gives some descriptive statistics of the results, distinguishing the two parts of the evaluation: the project and the written theory test. The total number of students evaluated is 327. This means that our analysis is based upon 327 individual written tests and 81 group projects, which involved the same 327 students. Comparing grades obtained in groups to the ones obtained individually is interesting for verifying the effect of group working on the final performance of students. As shown, there is not any relevant difference between the two parts of the evaluations, in terms of mean, modal and median values. Standard deviation is limited. As concerns the difference between the two parts of the evaluation, the mean and median values are close to zero, even if the modal value is -2. So the project marks are somehow lower than the written test, and there is a higher standard deviation.

Table 2. Students results (the Italian marks range is 18-30. The maximum evaluation, "30 with merit", is usually translated in numbers as 33)

	Project	Written test	Difference (project – written test)
n. of students	327	327	
mean value	25,44	25,02	0,42
std. dev	3,28	3,81	4,61
modal value	25	26	-2
median value	25	25	0

Going more in depth in the two parts of the evaluation, figure 2 gives an overview of the distribution of the marks. This brings into evidence that there is some difference: even if the mean values are very similar and the median values are identical, the evaluation of the projects are more close to a very tight, normal distribution, while the evaluation of the written test is more uniformly distributed. In other words, the projects bring the majority of the evaluations towards the mean value.

Figure 2. Distribution of the students marks

The analysis of the correlation between the evaluation of the two parts, (not reported here for sake of brevity) suggests that there is no correlation.

Moving to an in depth analysis of the evaluation of projects, table 3 distinguishes the marks achieved by students in the five parts evaluated. The descriptive statistics reported here is referred to the 81 projects evaluated, each project referring to groups composed typically (with some exceptions) of 4 students.

Table 3. Evaluation of projects

	Concept development	Product design	Process design	Business plan	Project presentation
n. projects evaluated	81	81	81	81	81
Mean value	27,12	25,10	24,48	25,56	26,13
Std dev.	3,83	4,57	3,85	4,05	2,63
modal value	30	26	25	25	28
median value	27	26	25	26	26,75

Mean and especially modal values for those parts of the project that require mainly technical specialised skills (product and process design, business plan) are lower than those requiring the integration of different typologies of technical, non-technical and soft skills. We have also checked for correlations among the various parts of the project evaluations (Pearson), though it is not reported here for the sake of brevity. No statistically significant correlations have been found.

3.2. Discussion of results

The results illustrated above suggest some interesting issues concerning the effectiveness of design based learning when applied to the teaching of innovation to engineers. As described in section 2, innovation is intrinsically a discipline requiring the integration of technical engineering and non-engineering skills, as well as soft skills, such as team working, creativity, and leadership. How the Industrial Design course described in section 2 favours the integration of different typologies of skills is partially indicated by the evaluation of the presentation and concept design parts of the project. Indeed, these two parts are those that require the maximum level of integration of different typologies of skills, both soft/professional and technical. As the evaluation of these two parts presents the highest mean, and especially modal values, we can argue that the integration required has actually been achieved. Evaluation mean and modal values for the other parts of the project, which require more specialisation of technical engineering competences, are lower. This suggests that DBL, conducted by means of team work, is particularly effective precisely when there is the need to make students be able to use their competencies in an integrated

manner, applying both technical and professional/soft skills. As concerns the development and application of technical specialised skills, DBL does not seem to be so effective. This is also confirmed by the fact that the results of the individual written test are similar, or even lower, than those of the projects, especially when looking at the results of the three more technical parts. So, DBL with working groups does not seem to add great value when the teaching objective is the specialisation of technical competencies, while it is effective for supporting their integration.

Concerning the development of professional skills, the course on Industrial Design allows for the evaluation of some of them, such as the ability to function on multi-disciplinary teams, the ability to communicate effectively, and the capacity to understand the impact of engineering solutions in a global, economic, environmental, and societal context [5]. This set of skills can be evaluated by the marks achieved by students in their presentations given to the committees, which include external business experts. From this point of view, the results achieved by students are very positive, as the mean and modal values are both very high, especially in comparison with the three more technical parts of the project. Hence, it can be argued that the development of professional (or soft) skills can benefit from DBL with team working.

Some negative effects also emerge from our experience of DBL.

The marks achieved by students in the two parts of their evaluation are not correlated between them. Comparing the marks of the same student in two types of examination, individual and in group, is interesting especially in terms of effectiveness of two types of learning approaches, “passive” or “active”. Obviously, a deeper understanding of this lack of correlation requires investigating the topics of performance of individuals within groups and of teams’ dynamic [20; 21], which are out of the scope of this paper.

Furthermore, the project marks smooth over the evaluation, reducing the differences between good and bad students. This is an effect that can be related to the several difficulties that characterise project-led learning, such as differences in motivation and pace of work among team members, time management, interpersonal problems, and free-riding [20; 16; 21]. Such a smooth over effect, which could be perceived by students [16] may be negative in terms of motivation, and can reduce the willingness of students to actively participate in team working.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This paper deals with the issue of teaching innovation management to engineering, which is recognized as a crucial topics in most important engineering schools [26]. The paper presents the experience of a DBL course on the management of innovation for industrial engineers concerning the NPD process. In particular, two main results of this study are relevant. First, the paper proposes a model for designing courses on innovation and new product development, which could be used in engineering schools. Such a model, presented in figure 2, allows for tailoring the contents of the course in coherence with the specific technological fields of innovation, by changing technical engineering contents while maintaining the technical non-engineering ones. Second, the eight-year experience allows for drawing some tentative conclusions concerning the effectiveness of DBL in the field of the management of innovation. Our results suggest that such a learning approach seems to be effective for developing the ability to integrate technical engineering and non engineering skills and to develop professional “soft” skills. The DBL approach seems to be less effective for supporting the specialisation of technical competences, which are necessary in the field of innovation.

The study presents several limitations, especially concerning team formation. Indeed, we have adopted only self selected teams and thus we are not able to evaluate effects related, for example, to gender, type of background (Bachelor's), and age, which are relevant in team working. Future experiments could be conducted with instructor selected teams, in order to investigate whether and how such factors can influence the effectiveness of the approach. Future research could also be devoted to compare the results achieved in this study with those obtained through other teaching approaches, in order to verify the effectiveness of DBL. Another relevant limitation concerns the theoretical background, which is currently rather focused on problem-based learning, with limited attention to other teaching approaches and, more generally, to educational research. Hence, future effort could be devoted to enrich the theoretical background.

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